

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20770044>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th June 2026

Accepted: 18th June 2026

Online: 20th June 2026

KEYWORDS

water resources management, water security, irrigation, climate change, water-saving technologies, digitalization, sustainable development, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

Water resources play a critical role in ensuring sustainable socio-economic development, agricultural productivity, and environmental security in Uzbekistan. Given the country's dependence on irrigated agriculture and the increasing challenges posed by climate change and water scarcity, effective water resources management has become a strategic priority of state policy. This article examines the key directions of water sector reform in Uzbekistan, focusing on the modernization of water infrastructure, implementation of water-saving technologies, digitalization of water accounting systems, and strengthening of institutional mechanisms for water governance.

Since gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has attached great importance to the rational use, protection, and effective management of water resources. This priority is largely обусловuted by the country's reliance on irrigated agriculture, which remains one of the most important sectors of the national economy. Consequently, ensuring water security and improving the efficiency of water use have become strategic objectives of state policy.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has undertaken comprehensive reforms aimed at modernizing the water management system, improving water infrastructure, and increasing the efficiency of water resource utilization. Numerous legislative and institutional measures have been introduced to strengthen water governance and support sustainable agricultural development.

A significant step in this direction was the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020. In his address, the President emphasized the need to promote water-saving irrigation technologies, improve water monitoring systems, and introduce automated water accounting mechanisms. These measures are intended to enhance water-use efficiency, reduce water losses, and ensure sustainable agricultural production under conditions of increasing water scarcity.

Water security has become one of the most important global challenges of the twenty-first century. Rapid population growth, economic development, environmental degradation, and climate change have intensified pressure on available water resources worldwide. Uzbekistan is particularly vulnerable to these challenges due to its geographical location and dependence on transboundary rivers.

At the 78th Session of the United Nations General Assembly, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev highlighted the growing risks associated with climate change in Central Asia. According to his statement, regional temperatures have increased at a rate twice the global average, resulting in significant glacier loss and threatening the future flow of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers. If current trends continue, water availability per capita and agricultural productivity may decline substantially, creating serious risks for regional socio-economic stability.

To address these challenges, Uzbekistan has adopted the Water Sector Development Concept for 2020–2030. The Concept establishes strategic priorities aimed at ensuring reliable water supply, improving irrigation systems, modernizing water infrastructure, and promoting innovative technologies in water management.

Particular emphasis is placed on:

- introducing water-saving irrigation technologies;
- digitalizing water accounting and monitoring systems;
- modernizing hydraulic infrastructure;
- improving the reclamation status of irrigated lands;
- strengthening institutional mechanisms of water governance;
- expanding international cooperation in the field of water resources management.

The implementation of these measures is expected to increase water-use efficiency and strengthen national water security.

One of the major challenges facing the water sector is the aging condition of water management facilities. Many hydraulic structures have been operating for more than three decades and require modernization and reconstruction. Improving the safety and operational efficiency of these facilities has therefore become a key priority of government policy.

Large-scale investment projects supported by international financial institutions are being implemented to reconstruct canals, reservoirs, pumping stations, and irrigation systems. These initiatives contribute to reducing water losses and improving the reliability of water supply for agricultural and domestic needs.

The sustainable development of Uzbekistan largely depends on the effective management of water resources. Current reforms aimed at modernizing water infrastructure, introducing innovative technologies, and strengthening institutional capacity represent important steps toward ensuring long-term water security. Given the growing impacts of climate change and increasing water demand, continued investment in water-saving technologies, digital water management systems, and international cooperation will remain essential for the future development of the country's water sector.

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